

Presentation

Dear colleagues,

As the summer commences, we are pleased to deliver the sixth issue of the Pedagogy Series, housed on the ISA's Social Justice and Democratization Space. The goal of the Pedagogy Series is to facilitate global sharing of teaching practices and reflections dialogue between sociology educators. This issue features scholarship from three nations across three continents: South America (Brazil), Europe (Barcelona), and North America (United States).

We begin with the work of Marcelo Cigales (University of Brasilia) who reflexively asks, "why teach and learn sociology?" In answering this question, Cigales traces the historical development of sociological teaching in Brazil across three social fields: political, scientific, and pedagogical. Next, Ana Belén Cano-Hila, Karla Berrens, Marc Pradel-Miquel, and Gemma Vila (University of Barcelona) describe and reflect upon the implementation of an innovative two year problem-based learning program for the teaching of urban sociology. Our third paper, written by Jackie Bruce and Katherine McKee (North Carolina State University), connects pedagogy to its political implications beyond the walls of educational institutions to consider how leaders of social movements 'learn' to lead. Bruce and McKee problematize gendered and racialized interpretations of leadership and propose pedagogical strategies to forward an alternative paradigm of transformative leadership.

We thank you for your readership and hope you enjoy these thought-provoking pieces.

Sincerely,

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